

Spectrophotometric Studies of Rhenium Complexes with 4-amino 5-mercapto 3 phenyl 4 : 1 : 2 Triazole

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The reagent 4-amino-5-mercapto 3 phenyl 4 : 1 : 2 triazole forms a stable reddish brown complex with rhenium on reducing it with stannous chloride in 1(M) to 5(M) hydrochloric acid medium and the metal can be estimated by extractive photometry in chloroform medium. The system obeys Beer's Law from 2-38 ppm at 380 nm. The molar absorptivity is 5.21×10^3 and the Sandell's sensitivity is $0.0351 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The metal forms a 1 : 1 complex (metal to ligand) with the ligand. Stability constant (log K) of the Re-complex has been evaluated by the Leden (4.25), Rossotti and Rossotti (4.34), and Harvey and Manning (4.53) methods.

MANY organic reagents have been used for spectrophotometric determination of rhenium¹⁻¹².

Among these some thiocompounds and oximes are of particular importance. Some of these have narrow acidity ranges. Although few oxime derivatives⁹⁻¹² are sensitive in their colour reaction towards rhenium the methods lack selectivity. The molar absorptivity of Re-4-amino-5-mercapto 3 phenyl 4 : 1 : 2 triazole system can be compared satisfactorily with diethyl dithiophosphoric acid ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 6.2 \times 10^3$)², thioglycolic acid ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 2.77 \times 10^3$)³, unithiol ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 3.69 \times 10^3$)⁴, methyl-2-pyridylketoxime ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 3.83 \times 10^3$)⁹. It may be mentioned that though the reagents like 2,4-diphenyl-thiosemicarbazide⁵, 1-phenyl-2 thiourea⁶, α - α' dinaphthyl thiourea⁷, *o*-cyclohexanedione dioxime¹⁰ have been used as reagent for Re, but salient features like sensitivity, selectivity and ranges for estimation have not been given. When the values of ϵ_{max} of the Re-complex with the present reagent is compared with other system as cited above it can be concluded that the present system is little more sensitive with an added advantage that Re can well be estimated even in the presence of Mo(VI) and W(VI) which proves that the reagent is much more selective in its reaction with rhenium.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with 10 mm quartz transmission cells was used.

A standard rhenium(VII) solution was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed quantity of potassium perrhenate (Johnson Matthey) in double distilled water. The solution was standardised by Nitron's method.

A 0.2% (w/v) solution of 4-amino-5-mercapto 3 phenyl 4 : 1 : 2 triazole was prepared in absolute ethanol.

0.3535 M solution of stannous chloride (G.R.E., Merck) was prepared in 1M hydrochloric acid.

Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their chloride, sulphate or from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts. All other chemicals were of AR grade. Double distilled water was used for preparing all the solutions.

Recommended Procedure :

Absorbance Curve :

6.0 ml of 0.2% (w/v) reagent solution in absolute ethanol was added to a standard solution of perrhenate containing 1 ml of 0.25 mg/ml rhenium in a separatory funnel followed by 2 ml of 0.3535 M stannous chloride solution and hydrochloric acid to maintain the final acidity between 1(M)-5(M). At subsequent measurement acidity of HCl was maintained at 3(M). The solution was diluted to 25 ml with the addition of measured quantity of water and alcohol in the ratio of (1 : 1). This solution was then shaken with 12 ml of chloroform for 5 minutes. The organic extract was taken over anhydrous sodium sulphate in a 50 ml beaker and transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask after drying. The aqueous phase was washed twice, each time with 5 ml of the chloroform and these were combined with the previous extract, after drying over sodium sulphate. The final volume was made upto 25 ml with chloroform. This order was maintained throughout this work. A reagent blank without the addition of rhenium was also prepared. Absorbances of the reagent (.01 at 380 nm) were measured against chloroform blank and also that of the complex against reagent blank at various wavelengths. The complex showed maximum absorbance at 380 nm.

Results and Discussion

The colour intensity remained constant for 6 hours and the period of complete extraction in chloroform was 5 minutes. 4 ml of 0.2% reagent solution in absolute alcohol was quite enough for the full colour development of 10 ppm of rhenium. Addition of more reagent did not produce any adverse effect on the colour system. For subsequent measurements 6 ml of the reagent solution were found sufficient.

For maximum colour development, 1(M)-5(M) HCl medium is required.

It has been observed that 0.25 ml of 0.35M Tin(II) chloride solution was sufficient for full colour development though a higher concentration of the latter has no adverse effect. A 0.35M SnCl₂ solution was however always used.

Validity of Beer's Law, relative error, sensitivity and molar absorptivity :

Test solutions with different concentrations of rhenium were prepared by the recommended procedure. The system adheres to Beer's Law from 2-38 ppm.

The Ringbom's¹³ optimal concentration range for measurement was found to be from 5.90 ppm-14.20 ppm.

The relative error per 2% absolute photometric error¹⁴ was found to be 2.72.

The molar absorptivity as obtained from Beer's law is 5.212×10^3 at 380 nm and Sandell's sensitivity¹⁵ is $0.0351 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

Composition of the Complex :

The composition of the coloured complex was determined by Job's method of continuous variations¹⁶ and by the mole-ratio method¹⁷. For Job's method mixture (12 ml total) of equimolar solutions (5.37×10^{-4}) of the perrhenate and the reagent were treated as in the general procedure. The curve indicates that the complex contains rhenium and the reagent in the ratio 1 : 1. This result was confirmed by the mole-ratio method.

Effects of Diverse ions :

The effect of diverse ions on the rhenium determination was studied by adding a definite amount of foreign ion to a solution containing 10 ppm of rhenium proceeding as described under the recommended procedure. The results are shown in Table 1. From the table it can be understood that except for copper, platinum, palladium, bismuth

and thiocyanate the method is free from interference by other foreign ions.

TABLE 1—EFFECTS OF DIVERSE IONS Re=10 ppm

Ions	Amount Studied ppm	Ions	Amount Studied ppm
Mo(VI)	400	Ir(III)	400
V(V)	400	Pt(IV)	Interferes
W(VI)	400	Pd(II)	Interferes
Ti(IV)	400	Bi(III)	Interferes
U(II)	400	Cu(II)	Interferes
Ni(II)	400	ScN ⁻	Interferes
Mn(II)	400	NO ₂ ⁻	400
Zn(II)	400	EDTA	400
Cd(II)	400	Oxalate	400
Co(II)	400	PO ₄ ^m	400
Cr(III)	400	F ⁻	400
Fe(II)	400	Citrate	400
Ca(II)	400	BO ₃ ⁻	400
Mg(II)	400	Tartarate	400
Al(III)	400	SO ₄ ⁻	400

Degree of Dissociation and Stability Constant :

The value of α , the degree of dissociation was calculated from Harvey and Manning's equation¹⁸ and the instability constant K' was evaluated from the given equation.

$$K' = (m\alpha c)^m (n\alpha c)^n / C(1 - \alpha),$$

where $m=1$, $n=1$, c =concentration in this case. Then the stability constant k was calculated as $1/k'$. The stability constant k was also evaluated by Leden's method¹⁹ and verified with the help of Rossotti and Rossotti's method²⁰.

Leden's Method :

For evaluation of k we have assumed that the equilibrium concentrations of the ligand is equal to the total ligand concentrations. This assumption is found to be valid as is evident from the values of free ligand concentrations, calculated for each determination of absorbances.

The stability values obtained by considering the degree of complexation are given below :

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \psi_1 = \lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \frac{\phi - 1}{L} = \beta_1$$

where $\phi = \frac{C_M}{M}$ i.e., the ratio of total metal ion C_M

and free metal ion concentration $[M]$ in solution and ψ =subsidiary function.

To evaluate β_1 , ψ_1 was plotted against $[L]$, free ligand concentration. A straight line was obtained and the intercept gave the value of β_1 (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Leden's Method of Stability Constant
 O Re-4-Amino-5-mercapto-3 phenyl 4 : 1 : 2 triazole,

Nature of the line indicated that only one species. M : R as 1 : 1 was present in the system. The value of K_1 was 1.8×10^4 .

The results are tabulated in Table 1.

Rossotti-Rossotti's Method²⁰ :

This method is based on the absorbance of a complex dependent on the total concentrations of ligand and central group.

The absorbance of the coloured species ML, M and L is given by Beer's Law.

$$As = \gamma \{ \epsilon_0 [M] + \epsilon_1 [ML] + \epsilon_L [L] \} \quad \dots (1)$$

where As = absorbance of the solution and
 γ = length of the optical depth.

$\epsilon_0, \epsilon_1, \epsilon_L$, are the extinction coefficients of free metal [M], species [ML] and free ligand [L] respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} As &= \gamma \{ \epsilon_0 [M] + \epsilon_1 \beta_1 [M][L] + \epsilon_L [L] \} \\ &= \gamma [[M] \{ \epsilon_0 + \epsilon_1 \beta_1 [L] \} + \epsilon_L [L]] \\ &= \gamma (C_M \xi + \epsilon_L [L]) \quad \dots (2) \end{aligned}$$

where C_M = total metal concentration

$$\xi = \sum_0^1 \epsilon_n \alpha_n$$

where α_n = fraction of the metal in the form ML

$$\xi = \frac{As - \gamma \epsilon_L [L]}{C_M \gamma} = \frac{\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_1 \beta_1 [L]}{1 + \beta_1 [L]} \quad \dots (3)$$

Equation (3) may be written as

$$\frac{\xi - \epsilon_0}{[L]} = \beta_1 (\epsilon_1 - \xi) \quad \dots (4)$$

Since [M] has no absorbance under the experimental conditions the equation (4) reduces to

$$\xi/[L] = \beta_1 \epsilon_1 - \beta_1 \xi.$$

The plot of ξ/L as ordinate and ξ as abscissa gave a straight line of slope $-\beta_1$ and intercept $\beta_1 \epsilon_1$ (Fig. 2.)

$$K_1 = \beta_1 = 2.2 \times 10^4 \quad \epsilon_1 = 5.2 \times 10^3$$

The value of molar extinction coefficient obtained from Beer's Law as stated earlier shows a close resemblance with the value ($\epsilon = 5.21 \times 10^3$) obtained from graphical evaluation.

Fig. 2. Rossotti-Rossotti's Method of Stability Constant
 ● Re-4-Amino-5-mercapto-3 phenyl 4 : 1 : 2 triazole

TABLE 2—OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANT OF THE COMPLEX AT 27°

Method	K	log K
Harvey and Manning	3.42×10^4	4.53
Leden	1.80×10^4	4.25
Rossotti-Rossotti	2.2×10^4	4.34

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